

Corrigendum: Digital Transition and Waste Management in Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Operations Industry

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In the original article, there was an error concerning some specific terminology of the construction sector which have been incorrectly written. In particular, “Design Built” and “Design Bid Built” were incorrectly written. The correct terminology is “Design Build” and “Design Bid Build.” This has been corrected throughout the article.

The authors apologize for this error and state that this does not change the scientific conclusions of the article in any way. The original article has been updated.

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